

Synthesis of N-Benzoyl-N'-2-(4-Aryl-5-Arylazothiazolyl) Thiocarbamides as Potential Antineoplastics

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Various N-benzoyl-N'-2-(4-aryl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides were prepared by condensing 2-amino-4-aryl-5-arylazothiazoles with benzoyl isothiocyanate. These thiocarbamides were tested for their antineoplastic activity.

THERE has been growing interest during the last few years in compounds containing the $N-N-S$ or $O-N-S$ tridentate ligand system¹⁻⁵ or arylazo grouping^{6,7}. This interest stems mainly from certain interesting carcinostatic activities of heterocyclic carboxyaldehydes, thiosemicarbazones and interfering action of 5-arylazopyrimidines with nucleic acid synthesis. Moreover, various Schiff's bases from benzaldehyde, nitrogen mustard and thiazole-amine have been reported to possess antitumour activity⁸⁻¹⁰. As a part of general study directed towards the development of antineoplastics, Sharma *et al*¹¹ synthesised and studied the properties of a series of compounds having the mixed structure. They prepared some new potential antineoplastics viz. N-phenyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides having $N-N-S$ ligand, arylazo grouping and a modified azomethine linkage. Keeping the above facts in view various N-benzoyl-N'-2-(4-aryl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides (III) (Table 2) were prepared by condensing 2-amino-4-aryl-5-arylazothiazoles (I) with benzoyl isothiocyanate (II)^{12,13}.

2-Amino-4-aryl-5-arylazothiazoles (Table 1) required in this synthesis were prepared by coupling diazotised arylamines with 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles. The latter have been obtained by the reaction of substituted acetophenones with thiourea and iodine following the procedure of Dodson and King¹⁴.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-amino-4-aryl thiazoles¹⁴: Iodine (0.2 mol) was added to a slurry consisting of acetophenone (0.2 mol) and thiourea (0.4 mol). The reaction mixture was heated overnight on a steam bath. The mixture was cooled and washed with solvent ether. It was then diluted with water, heated until most of the solid had gone into solution and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and made alkaline with liquor ammonia. The 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles were precipitated which were recrystallised from dilute alcohol.

Preparation of 2-amino-4-aryl-5-arylazothiazoles¹¹: Arylamine (0.02 mol) was dissolved in 3 N HCl and cooled to 0°. Sodium nitrite (1.4 g; 0.02 mol) dissolved in water (25 ml) was added slowly. The diazonium salt solution was filtered to a well

Fig. 1

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TABLE 1—2-AMINO-4-ARYL-5-ARYLAZOTHIAZOLES (I) OBTAINED BY THE COUPLING OF ARYLDIAZONIUM CHLORIDE WITH 2-AMINO-4-ARYLTHIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R'	R=H		R=CH ₃		R=Cl	
		m.p. °C	Yield%	m.p. °C	Yield%	m.p. °C	Yield%
1.	H	198-194	80	190	77	295-296	79
2.	2-OH ₂	160-161	82	205-206	75.6	212-213	80.1
3.	3-OH ₂	167	82.5	172-173	77.2	219-220	79.2
4.	4-OH ₂	175	81	209-210	78.2	243	78.8
5.	2-OCH ₃	210-211	80.8	201-202	79	140-141	60.6
6.	4-OCH ₃	168-169	81.2	185	80.6	D	81
7.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	205-206	82.6	217-218	76.3	165-167	78.2
8.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	D	83	208-204	75	210-211	78.6
9.	4-Cl	198	78	229	79.6	238-239	76
10.	4-Br	206-207	77.5	D	80.1	D	77.2

TABLE 2—N-BENZOYL-N'-2-(4-ARYL-5-ARYLAZOTHIAZOLYL) THIOCARBAMIDES (III) OBTAINED FROM I AND II

Sl. No.	R'	R=H		R=CH ₃		R=Cl	
		m.p. °C	Yield%	m.p. °C	Yield%	m.p. °C	Yield%
1.	H	217	70	181-182	71.5	219	66
2.	2-OH ₂	173-180	69.2	197-198	69.2	182-184	62.5
3.	3-OH ₂	155-156	68.2	148-149	70.2	198	61
4.	4-OH ₂	197-198	38	175	68	198-194	68
5.	2-OCH ₃	203-205	66	185-187	67	177-179	65
6.	4-OCH ₃	175	68.5	144-146	67.3	247-248	65.8
7.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	225-226	67	165-166	64.2	201-202	62
8.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	239-240	66.2	209-210	64.8	195-196	60.1
9.	4-Cl	249	67.2	196	69.7	167-169	63.5
10.	4-Br	231	67.6	223-225	68.2	239-240	60.8

cooled solution of 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles (0.02 mol) and sodium acetate (5 g) in ethanol (50 ml). After 2 hr 2-amino-4-aryl-5-arylazothiazoles were filtered and washed with water and recrystallised from DMF/ethanol.

Preparation of benzoyl isothiocyanate^{13,14}: Ammonium thiocyanate (5 g) was dissolved in acetone (50 ml). Benzoyl chloride (2 ml) was added. The contents were heated on a water bath at a temperature of 60-70°. The solution was filtered to remove ammonium chloride and benzoyl isothiocyanate was obtained. Yield 60%. Liquid b_{10} 133-137°, b_{10} 119°. Found: C, 58.87; N, 8.58; S, 19.65. Calcd: C, 58.82; N, 8.57; S, 19.60%.

Preparation of N-benzoyl-N'-2-(4-aryl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides: A mixture of benzoyl isothiocyanate (1.63 g; 0.01 mol) and 2-amino-4-aryl-5-arylazothiazole (0.01 mol) in benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 4-5 hr on a steam bath. The solvent was removed and the residue was treated with petroleum ether (40-60) and then with solvent ether. The crystalline thiocarbamide so obtained was recrystallised from DMF/alcohol.

The ir spectrum of N-benzoyl-N'-2-(4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamide so prepared shows absorption due to stretching frequencies of C=S group in the region of 1370 cm^{-1} , C=O group in the region of 1690 cm^{-1} and -N=N- group in the region of 1610 cm^{-1} . Absorption due to stretching frequencies of thiazole nucleus lie in the region of 1585, 1470, 1340, 1020 and 810 cm^{-1} .

The purity of these compounds has been checked by tlc in benzene-ethylacetate mixture. All the new compounds prepared in this investigation were analysed satisfactorily for N and S.

Biological activity: Almost all the thiocarbamides tabulated in Table 2 were tested for their cytostatic and cytopathic activity in duck embryo fibroblast cell culture (in unstained preparation).

The compounds No. 2 and 5 (R=H) and 7 (R=Cl) in Table 2 have shown cytostatic activity; the compounds No. 1 (R=H), 4 and 5 (R=CH₃) have shown cytopathic activity; the compounds No. 4, 8 and 10 (R=H), 2 and 10 (R=CH₃) caused individual cell rounding. The other compounds did not show any effect.

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